

BBMRI-ERIC Use Cases

Editors: Petr Holub and Philip Quinlan

Contributors (in alphabetic order):

Araceli DiezFraile, Petr Holub, Michael Hummel, Klaus Kuhn,
Jan-Eric Litton, Heimo Müller, Philip Quinlan, Morris Swertz,
Frank Ückert, Dalibor Valík, Ondřej Vojtíšek, Gianluigi Zanetti

September 30, 2016
Document revision: 0.8

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Glossary

BBMRI-ERIC Directory	Information service by BBMRI-ERIC, providing highly aggregated data about the biobanks and their collections of biological material and data. Previously also known as BBMRI Catalogue. 17, 19
Common Service	A formal way of organizing full member countries of BBMRI-ERIC to provide services of common interest. 4
CS IT	Common Service on Information Technologies (IT). 19
ISO	International Organization for Standardization (ISO), http://www.iso.org/ . 4
ISO/TC	Technical Committee of International Organization for Standardization (ISO). 5, <i>see</i> ISO
MSC	Message Sequence Chart(s), standard schema for defining communication among components in distributed systems. Defined in ITU-T Z.120 [1]. See also [2] and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Message_sequence_chart . 17, 21, 24
P ³ G	Public Population Project in Genomics and Society, http://www.p3g.org/ . 5

1. Definition of Basic Terms

The purpose of this section is to set out a common understanding of the terms to be used with BBMRI-ERIC. These definitions will be used to promote harmonisation within the community but we recognise differences will exist between countries (and within countries) and these differences we shall try to document to aid communication.

The definition of the terms should be communicated with the ISO Technical Committee (ISO/TC) 276.¹

1.1. T-1 – Biobank

Biobanks (and Biomolecular Resources Centres) means collections, repositories and distribution centres of all types of human biological samples, such as blood, tissues, cells or DNA and/or related data such as associated clinical and research data, as well as biomolecular resources, including model- and micro-organisms that might contribute to the understanding of the physiology and diseases of humans.

NOTE 1: Different Biobank definitions do exist, such as the OECD definition,² the P³G³ and the OECD in the Best Practice Guidelines for BRCs [3] based on [4]. The definition in this document is taken from the BBMRI-ERIC business plan [5].

NOTE 2: Synonyms are: Bio-resource, Bio-repository

1.2. T-2 – BBMRI-ERIC biobank

A Biobank that has gone through the assessment of a national node and has signed the BBMRI-ERIC Partner Charter.

NOTE 1: The term Biobank can be used freely, except maybe in countries with a specific legal definition. It is required within BBMRI-ERIC to distinguish between biobank

¹ The contact is Dr. Jörg Geiger, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg, <joerg.geiger@uni-wuerzburg.de>, +49 (931) 201-47010.

² <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=7220>

³ <http://www.p3gobservatory.org/lexicon/list.htm>

as a general term, and “BBMRI-ERIC” (quality) checked biobank, as e.g., done in RD-Connect in the Biobank Assessment.⁴

1.3. T-3 – Biobank network

A Biobank network is a non-exclusive set of Biobanks. A Biobank can be a member of multiple Networks.

1.4. T-4 – Individual

This is an over-arching term to include those that have participated or donated samples in a Biobank.

NOTE 1: This term is used to try and remove the verb from the definition. The term participant or donor both imply a potentially different role - i.e. donating and participating have quite different meanings.

NOTE 2: Synonyms are: Patients, Donors, Participants, Public

1.5. T-5 – Primary Sample

A discrete portion of a body fluid, breath, hair or tissue taken for examination, study or analysis of one or more quantities or properties assumed to apply for the whole. (as defined by ISO 15189)

NOTE 1: Specimen is an equivalent term.

1.6. T-6 – Sample

A Sample is a quantity of tissue, blood, urine or other biologically derived material. It can include everything from subcellular structures (DNA) to cells, tissue (bone, muscle, connective tissue and skin), organs (e.g. liver, bladder, heart, kidney), blood, gametes (sperm and ova), embryos, fetal tissue, and waste (urine, faeces, sweat, hair and nail clippings, shed epithelial cells and placenta) that is contained in a uniquely identifiable container (e.g., a vial, a histology block – that is used to hold biological material and that can be uniquely identified by a machine readable label i.e. (a barcode)).

⁴ <http://catalogue.rd-connect.eu/web/rddcurator/biobank-assessment>

NOTE 1: An aliquot is a type of Sample with a specific meaning. An aliquot is specifically generated by the process of aliquoting - i.e. taking one sample and sub-dividing into multiple identical samples. Therefore an aliquot infers commonality between one of more Samples. A Sample is a generic term that does not infer any commonality.

NOTE 2: When a Biobank is asked for the number of samples in storage - this would be the total number of entities that are stored, therefore including already aliquoted material such as DNA or sections already taken from a FFPE Sample.

NOTE 3: When a Biobank divides a sample for release to a researcher (such as aliquoting DNA or taking a section from an FFPE block) the Biobank is expected to record the creation of these as new Samples within the Biobank, therefore temporarily increasing the total number of samples in the Biobank. Once released the sample count will return to normal (assuming the original Sample was not exhausted during the process). This is to ensure that accurate recording of Sample 'stock' and Sample use is accurate.

1.7. T-7 – Sample Collection

A sample collection is a set of Samples (partition) belonging to a partitioning of the parent sample set, which is either a Biobank or another Sample Collection. Samples in each sample collection share at least one common property.

NOTE 1: A Biobank is free to define a collection at their own discretion.

NOTE 2: There should be at least one collection in each biobank, which covers the whole biobank.

NOTE 3: Splitting into child is possible, e.g., based on life cycle of the material and followed Standard Operating Procedures.

1.8. T-8 – BBMRI-ERIC Directory

BBMRI-ERIC IT service providing metadata about biobanks and their collections, implementing S+UCs-1 (“Biobank browsing/lookup”).

1.9. T-9 – Sample/Data Negotiator

BBMRI-ERIC IT service facilitating access to samples, data, and services of BBMRI-ERIC biobanks. It implements S+UCs-2 (“Biobank access negotiation”).

1.10. T-10 – Sample/Data Locator

BBMRI-ERIC IT service providing (automated) querying for availability statistics of samples and data in BBMRI-ERIC biobanks, supporting complex queries about parameters of samples, data, and donors.

1.11. T-11 – Biobank Connector

Well-defined IT interface (API specification + reference implementation) for BBMRI-ERIC to connect to a BBMRI-ERIC biobank.

NOTE 1: Primary use for purposes of T-10 (“Sample/Data Locator”), but expected to be used for other purposes such as automated population of T-8 (“BBMRI-ERIC Directory”).

1.12. T-12 – Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS)

A Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) is a software that support laboratory’s operations, covering e.g. analysis workflows, sample tracking, data tracking, data exchange, quality monitoring, billing and reporting.

1.13. T-13 – Biobank Information Management System (BIMS)

A Biobank Information Management System (BIMS) is a software that supports biobank operations, covering sample storage and inventory, kit assembly and distribution, sample shipping, sample quality management, sample access management, device management and administrative/ business support.

2. Description of Users

The services to be offered will encompass a diverse group of users. These users are expected to have different levels of knowledge (both technical and domain) and will have different and potentially conflicting interests. This section is to establish the different types of users, their likely needs and use-cases and conflicts that may exist between them. The Agile approach to the development of the service shall allow the different users to have input to the design phases, however, it equally must be recognised that not all the users needs (especially when conflict exists) will always be accommodated in every stage of the developments.

This chapter is accompanied by the list of “Personas” (model persons) created by BBMRI.uk in Appendix A on page 28.

2.1. U-1 – Bio/Medical researchers

The bio/medical researchers are exemplified in the 'Searching Sally' persona. Searching Sallys will be searching for the availability of a range of biosamples (possibly also non-human biosamples) and the availability of accompanying data that are fit-for-purpose. Rather than seeking the exact Sample, Sally will often be seeking Biobanks that are able to provide the samples, data and/or services that are required. Sally will have an in-depth understanding of the research she wishes to undertake but not necessarily how that translates into a search for samples and/or biobanks. Therefore, she may not know the exact requirements, such as the types of samples, preservation methods or quality samples that are most suitable for the research she wishes to undertake - Sally may not actually know what she is searching for other than finding centres of expertise than can help. In addition, they are unlikely to have IT knowledge beyond the standard office skill-set. The sub-groups are to capture different scenarios in which Sally could operate.

2.1.1. Research driven

This sub-group is to represent researchers who may come to the BBMRI-ERIC service with a strong understanding about the research question they wish to answer and even the dataset (at a high level) they may need to answer those questions. They are unaware if that dataset already exists or if samples will be required and if so, what samples will be appropriate. The motivation for coming to the service is to directly support or drive new research - samples are a means to an end.

User interests:

- Q-1_{U-1}** I want to undertake a population level research project and i think I need samples (with data) in order to answer specific research questions but I am unsure of the type and quality that would be most appropriate
- Q-2_{U-1}** I want to undertake a specific research project on a sub-set of disease based on a routine phenotype. I need to know that the biobanks can provide me with the necessary samples and more importantly that they have the data to ensure correct stratification.
- Q-3_{U-1}** I want to see what samples and data are available in order to generate new research ideas and collaborations.
- Q-4_{U-1}** I have a research project proposal and I want to make reservation for the samples so that they are not depleted before my proposal gets approval.

2.1.2. Protocol development

This sub-group is to represent researchers who are at a different stage of the research process. They only require a small number of samples but ideally they seek to test on a diverse set of samples as possible. Such a requirement may mean a local Biobank cannot supply the required diversity.

User interests:

- Q-5_{U-1}** I am developing a new lab-based method and require access to low number of samples but from a broad range of diseases to test the suitability across multiple domains
- Q-6_{U-1}** I wish to test for the presence of a specific compound and wish to find samples from a broad range of diseases to test the suitability across multiple domains

2.1.3. Specific requirements

This sub-group is to represent researchers that have a much greater understanding of the samples they require.

User interests:

- Q-7_{U-1}** I have a research project and I have an understanding about the samples and data that are required. I am looking for samples and/or data.
- Q-8_{U-1}** I have already undertaken a research project and I wish to replicate/expand, therefore I know the exact requirements. I am looking for samples and/or data.
- Q-9_{U-1}** I have dealt with my local Biobank successfully and I now require to extend the scope and therefore I am looking for similar Biobanks across BBMRI-ERIC. I am looking for samples and/or data.
- Q-10_{U-1}** I want to find a Biobank to take care of long-term storage of all the samples of my study or my research project that I am planning.

2.2. U-2 – Data driven researchers

Data Dave Persona to be created. Dave does not necessarily have the wet lab capabilities to undertake new research on samples but is interested in conducting research utilising data that has already been generated from samples. These users are likely to develop their own IT systems in order to proceed with their research, however, some tools developed by the service may be utilised. In addition the data driven researchers may be required to support a local Biobank due to their technical knowledge. This support is often not funded and can place pressures on time, in such a scenario tools for local Biobanks may also be sought.

User interests:

Q-11_{U-2} What Biobanks have a data return policy?

Q-12_{U-2} I need to discover datasets in order to contemplate what is possible

Q-13_{U-2} I require a confirmatory dataset and I am searching for exact data points

Q-14_{U-2} I wish to undertake meta level analyses without requiring data downloads

Q-15_{U-2} Are there data tools that will streamline my research?

Q-16_{U-2} Are there data tools that will assist my local Biobank?

Q-17_{U-2} I have developed some tools which i believe can benefit the community but do not have a mechanism to get them utilised beyond by local Institute. 7

2.3. U-3 – Industrial R&D

Industrial R&D are likely to have many of the same questions as the Bio/Medical Researchers. This user group differs from the previous group namely in terms of high requirements on quality standards. Currently, industry mostly works with the biobanks in a way that they identify biobanks they seem to be capable of working with the stringent standards and then proposing a common project, typically creating consistent sample study from scratch. In many cases they are also seeking fresh samples, rather than accessing historically preserved samples.

User interests:

Q-18_{U-3} I want to find a biobank that has good potential for collaboration (it can handle quality procedures, it has some shared interests).

Q-19_{U-3} I want to find a biobank that has the capability to provide fresh samples at the necessary quality.

2.4. U-4 – Biobankers

A T-1 (“Biobank”) can have many different operating, funding and reward mechanisms. These must be understood if the aims of BBMRI-ERIC are to be achieved. Rather than split this section into different types of Biobanks based on the samples or research activities, the grouping

is based on common funding and reward mechanisms. Their motivations are likely to differ but there are some over-arching common fears.

Motivations:

- The burden of participation will exceed any benefit
- I am willing to participate but my current biobanking software does not allow any changes
- I am willing to participate but adapting my current biobanking software will be prohibitively expensive
- I will be expected to change my underlying database
- I will be expected to change my underlying processes
- I will not be able to recover my actual costs

User interests:

Q-20_{U-4} What are similar biobanks to mine? (Similarity can be judged based on a number of different parameters and the algorithms need to be able to accommodate them.)

2.4.1. Nationally funded Biobank

These Biobanks represent a coordinated effort at a national level. These Biobanks enjoy backing at a governmental level and therefore can be backed by necessary legislative powers to ensure effective running and financial backing to ensure it remains a sustainable resource.

Motivations:

- We are funded under a national remit and we need to demonstrate use of the Biobank. BBMRI-ERIC is a mechanism for generating new interest for our Biobank.
- We can demonstrate the national importance of partaking in BBMRI-ERIC

2.4.2. Researcher or Clinician led Biobank

Many Biobanks originate from a personnel need to have access to samples. These Biobanks would be led by a researcher or clinician who has the ability to collect samples, whether they be a pathologist or a researcher based in a clinical setting. These Biobanks were established to satisfy a very local need and therefore there is an inherent conflict introduced when extending the Biobank to external use. In addition, these Biobanks are usually funded by research-led questions that have a need for samples, therefore, the Biobank is sustained because of the researcher or clinician continuing their research programme. The ability to secure research-led funding is also made more credible by the presence of their own Biobank. Finally the researchers or clinicians will be rewarded by the Institutions based on their research activity or clinical excellence and not the successful running of the Biobank.

Therefore these Biobanks represent a complex mix of personnel interests which can result in sharing samples actually disadvantaging the Biobank.

Motivations:

- Participating in world-leading research
- Maintaining research reputation or clinical excellence
- protect the content of the biobanks from both the perspective of physical sample and data security

Fears:

- The samples I have worked hard to collect will become available to all
- I will be supporting other peoples research at the expense of my own 'day job'
- Loss of control
- Giving other people access to samples could create competition for funding

2.4.3. BaaS – Biobank-as-a-Service

These Biobanks are run with the aim of providing a service to the community. These are quite different to the Researcher or Clinician led Biobank as their success is deemed by the continued use of the Biobank. These Biobanks may have some external funding to support some of the activities but many will operate a cost-recovery model in order to sustain the Biobank long-term.

Motivations:

- recovering their operational costs both in short- and long-term, including technology/equipment/facilities and staff
- seeking research impact by having samples in the biobanks used in world-leading researchers
- Be seen to deliver a high quality service

Fears:

- demand may exceed the ability to fulfill the requests
- cost recovery model will be over-ridden by BBMRI-ERIC
- researchers will perceive them to be expensive

2.5. U-5 – Software Vendors

Software Vendors often provide the T-13 (“Biobank Information Management System (BIMS)”) for the Biobanks. The feature sets of these software packages can vary greatly. In particular

the level of capacity to share and extract data can vary greatly. Therefore when seeking to integrate Biobanks into any cohesive network it is important to factor in that although the Biobank may be willing, their T-13 (“Biobank Information Management System (BIMS)”) may not facilitate it. An understanding of the variability of the software packages being used is a clear requirement of the IT Common Service. In addition, it is important to understand the motivations of Software Vendors.

Motivations:

- demonstrating capacity in a developing area can both boost sales and improve retention of existing customers
- engagement from groups such as BBMRI-ERIC allow us to stay informed about future requirements and therefore reducing the risk to our business

Fears:

- we will be expected to implement changes without being engaged about how those changes should be implemented
- there is no single recognised body, how do we know this investment is worthwhile

2.6. U-6 – Funding bodies

Various organizations supporting research or R&D. Two types funding can be differentiated, depending on the target funding:

Infrastructure funding bodies *User interests:*

Q-21_{U-6} What is the extent of infrastructure funded?

Q-22_{U-6} What is the utilization of infrastructure funded?

Project funding bodies

Q-23_{U-6} Are there high-quality resources credibly available for the proposed research? (as a part of research proposal reviews)

Q-24_{U-6} Is the project proposal proposing collection of samples utilizing biobanks to achieve quality-defined sample and data retrieval, processing, and processing? (as a part of research proposal reviews)

2.7. U-7 – BBMRI-ERIC (whole infrastructure)

The BBMRI-ERIC needs to support and stimulate development of the biobanking and biomolecular resources as well as their utilization.

User interests:

Q-25_{U-7} We want to demonstrate extent of the infrastructure and its utilization in generating novel research and applied results, in order to show importance to policy makers.

Q-26_{U-7} We want to increase utilization of the biobanking and biomolecular resources.

2.8. U-8 – BBMRI-ERIC National Nodes

BBMRI-ERIC national nodes support communication with the participating biobanks on the national level, following the hub and spoke architecture of the BBMRI-ERIC.

User interests:

Q-27_{U-8} We want to demonstrate extent of the national infrastructure and its utilization in generating novel research and applied results, in order to show importance to policy makers on the national level.

2.9. U-9 – Research participants, patients and their organizations

These users include both research participants and their organizations, as well as advocacy groups that support either bio/medical research or that pursue patients rights. They are interested in either demonstrating usefulness of giving their samples and data for the research, or in withdrawing consent either specifically for some cases, or generally, or in effectiveness of research performed toward generating new treatment strategies.

NOTE 1: The term “participants” has been introduced to cover both “donors” (population biobanks/cohorts) and “patients”. This is standardized in OECD guidelines. [6]

User interests:

Q-28_{U-9} I want to identify biobanks that potentially have my samples and data in order to see what research they are supporting (or doing themselves).

Q-29_{U-9} I want withdraw my consent in general and I do not have copies of the consents I have signed in the past. Thus I want to identify biobanks (or even healthcare provides that provide the data/material for the research) that potentially have my samples and data in order to approach them and withdraw the consent.

3. Systems and Use Cases

3.1. S+UCs-1 – Biobank browsing/lookup

This is the most trivial use case, where the requester wants to find out information on biobanks, ranging from the listing all available biobanks, to selection of biobanks based on metadata information.

Figure 3.1.: UML use case diagram for S+UCs-1 (“Biobank browsing/lookup”).

The user can browse:

Figure 3.2.: Overview of interaction of components of BBMRI-ERIC Directory, modeled using MSC.

- in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory, through all the biobanks of the BBMRI-ERIC,
- in the national Directory, through the national biobanks,
- search through the national biobanks should also give a link or even live results from the BBMRI-ERIC Directory in a separate section (i.e., “these are the relevant national biobanks and if yo are interested, this is a selection of relevant biobanks outside of your national biobanks” semantics).

3.1.1. Addressed user questions

- Bio/Medical researchers (U-1)
 - Q-7_{U-1} - *partial*
 (“I have a research project and I have an understanding about the samples and data that are required. I am looking for samples and/or data.”)
 - Q-4_{U-1} - *partial*
 (“I have a research project proposal and I want to make reservation for the samples so that they are not depleted before my proposal gets approval.”)
 - *Comment:* The users wants to find biobanks that are potentially relevant to his research. Potential relevance assessment relies on extent and accuracy of metadata

published by each biobank. Further communication about the samples is directly between the user and the biobank.

- Data driven researchers (U-2)
 - Q-11_{U-2} - *full*
("What Biobanks have a data return policy?")
 - Q-12_{U-2} - *partial*
("I need to discover datasets in order to contemplate what is possible")
 - ditto as Bio/Medical researchers.
- Industrial R&D (U-3)
 - Q-18_{U-3} - *partial*
("I want to find a biobank that has good potential for collaboration (it can handle quality procedures, it has some shared interests).")
 - Q-19_{U-3} - *partial*
("I want to find a biobank that has the capability to provide fresh samples at the necessary quality.")
 - *Comment:* ditto as Bio/Medical researchers.
- Research participants, patients and their organizations (U-9)
 - Q-29_{U-9} - *partial*
("I want withdraw my consent in general and I do not have copies of the consents I have signed in the past. Thus I want to identify biobanks (or even healthcare providers that provide the data/material for the research) that potentially have my samples and data in order to approach them and withdraw the consent.")
- BBMRI-ERIC (whole infrastructure) (U-7)
 - Q-25_{U-7} - *full*
("We want to demonstrate extent of the infrastructure and its utilization in generating novel research and applied results, in order to show importance to policy makers.")
- BBMRI-ERIC National Nodes (U-8)
 - Q-27_{U-8} - *full*
("We want to demonstrate extent of the national infrastructure and its utilization in generating novel research and applied results, in order to show importance to policy makers on the national level.")
- Biobankers (U-4)
 - Q-20_{U-4} - *full*
("What are similar biobanks to mine? (Similarity can be judged based on a number of different parameters and the algorithms need to be able to accommodate them.)")

3.1.2. Interests in this usecase

Biobankers (U-4).

- This user wants to minimize overhead due to having biobank connected to some upstream system. This includes minimization of manual input, which is particularly important when the system is not automated to the level of individual infor-

mation systems where the primary information is stored. The user should also not be forced to retype any information previously provided.

- This user wants to demonstrate the value of the biobank.
- This user is responsible for protecting the data.
- This user may want to see other biobanks and may be interested more specifically in the biobanks that are in some criteria comparable to his/her biobank.
- This user is concerned about overhead related to participate in several services of such a type.¹

Funding bodies (U-6).

To see/verify the extent of the BBMRI-ERIC ecosystem when considering funding of infrastructures. To see/verify availability of biobanks when some of the users applies for funding of research projects.

3.1.3. Benefits/incentives for users

Biobankers (U-4). • Findability = increased visibility in their biobank, likely resulting in increased utilization.

Bio/Medical researchers (U-1). • Centralized/simplified lookup of resources = decreased cost in procuring research resources.

Data driven researchers (U-2). • Centralized/simplified lookup of resources = decreased cost in procuring research resources.

3.2. S+UCs-2 – Biobank access negotiation

This use case is the simplest approach to obtain availability information on samples/data from biobanks.

3.2.1. Addressed user questions

- Bio/Medical researchers (U-1)
→ Q-1_{U-1} – *full*
("I want to undertake a population level research project and i think I need samples (with data) in order to answer specific research questions but I am unsure of the type and quality that would be most appropriate ")

¹ During the Common Service IT User Forum discussion, this has been particularly mentioned as an issue with participating in BBMRI-ERIC Directory, ISBER Resrouce Locator, etc.

Figure 3.3.: UML use case diagram for S+UCs-2 (“Biobank access negotiation”).

- Q-7_{U-1} - *full*
 (“I have a research project and I have an understanding about the samples and data that are required. I am looking for samples and/or data.”)
- Q-4_{U-1} - *full*
 (“I have a research project proposal and I want to make reservation for the samples so that they are not depleted before my proposal gets approval.”)
 - *Comment:* The users wants to get access to the samples/data with given (in advance known) parameters. Request refinement is expected as a part of this process, as the original request may come (and often comes) underspecified.
- Q-2_{U-1} - *full*
 (“I want to undertake a specific research project on a sub-set of disease based on a routine phenotype. I need to know that the biobanks can provide me with the necessary samples and more importantly that they have the data to ensure correct stratification. ”)

3.2.2. Interests in this usecase

Biobankers (U-4).

- minimize overhead
- optimize utilization of biobank resources
- allow for access control to samples/data with support for request prioritization

Bio/Medical researchers (U-1).

Data driven researchers (U-2).

Figure 3.4.: Sequence chart of interaction of a requester with biobankers via Sample/Data Negotiator tool, modeled using MSC.

- prevent biobankers from stealing my research ideas

3.2.3. Benefits/incentives for users

3.3. S+UCs-3 – Brokering Biobanking Services: Virtual lab facility

This use case describes the integration of multiple facilities – possibly located in different physical sites – in a single virtual facility that provides users with a one-stop-shop solution. At the same time, the emphasis is on guaranteeing a continuous enrichment process of the physical biobanks by systematically adding new digital data windows on the same biological material.

To be concrete we will consider a specific example directly relevant to currently running research projects.

1. A collection of FFPE samples, possibly coming from different biobanks, is selected by matching of a specific clinical profile.

2. The FFPE blocks are shipped to one/more facilities where tissue slides are prepared, stained and digitally scanned.
3. The digital tissue slides are associated to the FFPE blocks but access to the slides is restricted to the study participants and embargoed to everybody else.
4. A group of anatomic-pathologists participating to the study remotely access the images, classify them and explicitly select, and appropriately tag, ROIs (Region of Interest) on the digital slides.
5. A facility extracts tissue samples from the FFPE blocks in correspondence of the selected ROIs.
6. The latter are analyzed using -omic technologies and the results linked back to the ROIs. As before, the results enrich the biosamples but they are embargoed until needed (or an embargo deadline has been reached).

3.4. S+UCs-4 – Brokering Biobanking Services: Continuous integration with clinical facilities

This use case describes the integration of a clinical facility (e.g., clinical lab, pathology) to a biobank sample acquisition process.

The underlying idea is that it is possible to harness existing, well established, clinical informatics approach to seamlessly feed biobanks from clinics.

3.5. S+UCs-5 – Search for samples based on sample attributes

3.5.1. Addressed user questions

- Bio/Medical researchers (U-1)
 - Q-1_{U-1} - *full*
 - (“I want to undertake a population level research project and i think I need samples (with data) in order to answer specific research questions but I am unsure of the type and quality that would be most appropriate ”)
- Data driven researchers (U-2)
 - Q-12_{U-2} - *full*
 - (“I need to discover datasets in order to contemplate what is possible”)

Figure 3.5.: UML use case diagram for S+UCs-5 (“Search for samples based on sample attributes”).

3.5.2. Interests in this usecase

Bio/Medical researchers (U-1).

Biobankers (U-4).

- This user wants to minimize overhead due to having biobank connected to some upstream system.
- This user wants to show the value of the biobank.
- This user is responsible for protecting the data.

Specifically for the biobankers, who are also researchers:

- This user wants to protect their competitive advantage if they do their own research.

http://mhc.genetools.sourceforge.net/v5.2.1

Figure 3.6.: Sequence chart of interaction of a requester with biobankers via Sample/Data Locator tool, modeled using MSC.

3.6. S+UCs-6 – Search for samples based on specific individuals

Use case to be defined.

3.7. S+UCs-7 – Search for samples based donor attributes

Use case to be defined.

3.8. S+UCs-8 – Withdrawal of the informed consent

Use case to be defined.

3.8.1. Interests in this usecase

Research participants, patients and their organizations (U-9).

3.9. S+UCs-9 – Maintenance of study-based data for the clinicians

Use case to be defined.

3.10. S+UCs-10 – Community building for the biobankers – getting updates from other updates

Use case to be defined.

3.11. S+UCs-11 – Use increased performance of a biobank to increase its incentives

Use case to be defined.

3.12. S+UCs-12 – Hosting services for the national nodes

Use case to be defined.

3.13. S+UCs-13 – Reference tools for the bionanks to connect to a national node

Use case to be defined.

3.14. S+UCs-14 – Open-source LIMS system

Use case to be defined.

3.15. S+UCs-15 – Platform for Sensitive Data Processing

Use case to be defined.

3.16. S+UCs-16 – Structured data extraction from clinical records

Use case to be defined.

3.17. S+UCs-17 – Tools for translations of ontologies

Use case to be defined.

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A. BBMRI.uk Personas

The “Personas” have been created as a part of the BBMRI.uk effort to analyze users’ requirements on the design of BBMRI.uk services.

“If they're removing something anyway, it might as well do some good. Just don't use it for evil – or worse – pass my medical information to insurance companies!”

Joe's story:

Joe has never been in need of medical testing beyond a few blood tests, and he plans to stay that way. His father died of a heart attack, and Joe tries to stay healthy to avoid doing the same. He can't recall ever hearing of tissue banking before, but he can hazard a guess that it's not about stockpiling Kleenex. He's never been asked to donate tissue for research purposes, but thinks it's a good idea, provided that everything's above-board, and the samples and data don't fall into the wrong hands.

If he wanted to learn more or get involved, he'd ask his doctor, but he'd probably wait to be contacted. He's not *that* interested.

Goals

- Information
 - Understand what tissue banking is and how it works
 - Check that the biobank is doing worthwhile research
 - Find out what studies are being done with tissue like his
 - Learn about what he'd have to do to donate
 - See what protections are in place for him as a donor
- Action
 - Register his interest
 - Arrange a time and location to donate

Needs

- Information
 - What do I have to do?
 - How long will it take?
 - What will happen to my sample?
 - Who is in charge?
 - What are the terms and conditions?
 - Will my sample be used commercially?
 - Could my sample be traced back to me?
 - Could an insurance company access my data?
 - How safe is my data?
- Action
 - Introduction from a trusted source
 - Option to revoke consent
 - Live help chat
 - Control over future contact from Biobanks
 - Alert when a study which may have used his sample is published
 - Input form for registering interest and arranging donation

Reasons to get involved

Reasons not to get involved

Figure 1. User journey from learning about tissue banking to arranging to donate

“We have so many samples which could be put to good use. But how are we going to make it work?”

Barbara’s story:

Barbara oversees a group of biobanks, primarily focused on diagnosing cancer risk factors. These biobanks have an ongoing relationship with local hospitals, which collect samples on their behalf.

Barbara’s biobanks use a bespoke system to keep records of stored samples, and allow for search, retrieval, and tracking. It works well enough, but it’s largely for internal use. External researchers prefer to call or email to talk about their needs, and this ensures that the right samples are sent out for their needs – researchers often need a lot of help identifying the right samples

Goals

- Cut down on **time** spent figuring out what researchers actually **need** (as opposed to what they say they want)
- **Streamline** the application process, and not go back and forth over issues like ethics, consent, MTA, etc.
- Be more **visible** to researchers and the public
- Maintain a **good reputation**

Action

- **Track** how samples are used in research, and ensure proper attribution

Needs

- **Standardised terms** to make searching consistent
- **Comprehensive information** about the biobank, so that researchers are aware of operating procedures and application requirements before enquiring
- **Standard consent, ethics, and MTA forms** which are consistent with the biobank’s requirements
- A **lay summary** of biobank activities, so that a member of the public can learn about the biobank

- A **simple** system which can deal with any amount of data
- A **secure** system that won’t risk the privacy of patients, or integrity of the data
- A **straightforward** system that won’t require the input of large amounts of data

PhD in Biosciences

Well versed in medical terms

Familiar with legal requirements for human tissue sample collection, and own ethical samples

Reasons to get involved

Reasons not to get involved

Figure 1. Desired user journey from sample collection to Biobanks entry

Figure 2. Desired user journey when dealing with requests (including enquiries for samples and prospective collection)

“This has the potential to make my life a lot easier, but it requires a lot of trust that the tissue bank is doing everything by the book”

Sally’s story:

Sally is part of a team conducting breast cancer research. Her department has a small in-house biobank, and she has worked with other biobanks in the past, learning of them through word-of-mouth. She finds it very helpful to be able to speak to the biobank administrator and work out together exactly what samples she should be ordering. She has learned that flexibility is vital when you’re looking for samples! If she can’t get the samples she needs from the biobanks she has access to, she has to arrange to collect new samples, which can be costly and time-consuming, but at least she can be sure the collection is exactly what she needs

PhD in Cell Biology

Well versed in medical terms from own field of research

Familiar with legal requirements for human tissue sample collection, and own ethical samples

- Information**
 - Check that the biobank she wants to order from adheres to an appropriate set of operating **standards**
 - Check the biobank’s **reputation** for providing usable samples
 - Verify the presence or absence of appropriate samples for the purposes of writing a **grant** application
 - Check if the biobank is a good **collaborative partner**
- Action**
 - Access** larger or more diverse sets of samples than would normally be available
 - Conduct **proof-of-concept** work using ordered samples to justify fresh collection

- Information**
 - A **directory** of participating biobanks, searchable by research area
 - Information reflecting the biobank’s **operating procedures**
 - A list of **research papers** the biobank has provided samples for
 - Information on the biobank’s stance on **attribution** in published works
 - As much **information** as possible about the sample — disease and tissue type, preparation and storage, subject data, etc.
- Action**
 - A method of interrogating biobanks’ databases with both **general and specific terms**
 - Method of **communicating** directly with a biobank
 - A print-out or other form of **verification** to include in grant applications

Reasons to get involved

Reasons not to get involved

Figure 1. Desired user journeys branching from initial search term to contact with biobank

“We demand the highest standard from our suppliers. It’s not just about the type and quality of the samples they can provide, the biobank must be of the highest quality too”

Paul’s story:

Paul is the procurement manager for a major pharmaceutical company based in the UK. Obtaining the right samples for his researchers can be tricky, as existing samples often don’t have consent for commercial use included, and there isn’t a system in place to let them collect samples directly from hospitals. If they want fresh samples, they sometimes have to order them from America!

When a researcher finds a biobank they want to use, Paul has to ensure that everything is done right – legally and ethically, as well as procedurally. If a biobank passes muster, a contract is drawn up for collection. This makes sure that the biobank continues to maintain the required standard.

Goals

- Information**
 - Find biobanks with the **required capabilities**
 - Streamline the process of vetting biobanks to reduce project turnaround time
 - Identify biobanks with a **good reputation** for collecting samples
 - Identify **reliable biobanks** for an ongoing collection arrangement
- Action**
 - Access** high quality samples from trained clinicians and researchers
 - Meet the specific needs of his researchers

Needs

- Information**
 - A **directory** of participating biobanks, searchable by research area or population access
 - Access to a biobank’s **certifications and training records** to verify standards
 - Access to biobank’s **procedures** for sample collection
 - Access to biobank’s **ethics and consent** forms
 - Estimates of **costs and timeframes** for collection
 - A list of **research papers** the biobank has provided samples for
- Action**
 - A method of communicating directly with a biobank
 - A method of searching for similar biobanks

Reasons to get involved

Reasons not to get involved

Figure 2. Desired user journey for vetting a biobank for prospective collection

Figure 1. Desired user journey for a pharmaceutical researcher seeking samples